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Impact of Fuel Subsidy Removal on Public Sector Budgeting and Financial Reporting in Nigeria: Evidence from 2023–2025

Akaegbobi, Tochukwu Nkem. PhD, FCFA, FBDFM¹ & Duezeh Emmanuel Afamefuna PhD²

¹Department of Accountancy,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

²Department of Marketing, Faculty of Management Sciences,
Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The removal of fuel subsidy in Nigeria on 29 May 2023 marked a structural shift in public finance. This study examines how the policy affected public sector budgeting and financial reporting between 2023 and 2025. Using secondary data from the Federation Account Allocation Committee, Debt Management Office, National Bureau of Statistics, NEITI, and the World Bank, the study finds that FAAC allocations rose by 79% in 2024 compared to 2023, increasing fiscal space for states and local governments. However, challenges remain in transparency of subsidy savings, partial remittance by NNPC Limited and absorption of gains by debt servicing. Content analysis of audited financial statements shows limited separate disclosure of subsidy savings, contrary to IPSAS requirements. The study concludes that while subsidy removal improved revenue inflows, weak disclosure practices and fiscal indiscipline limit its impact on service delivery. Recommendations include full IPSAS compliance, establishment of a ring-fenced subsidy savings fund, and independent monitoring of fund utilization.

Keywords: Fuel Subsidy Removal, Public Sector Budgeting, Financial Reporting

1. INTRODUCTION

For over four decades, Nigeria operated a fuel subsidy regime that consumed a large share of public revenue. The subsidy was intended to cushion the effect of global crude oil price volatility on domestic consumers. However, it became fiscally unsustainable and a conduit for corruption. By 2022, subsidy payments reached ₦4 trillion, accounting for 61.4% of oil revenue and contributing to Nigeria's failure to remit oil proceeds to the Federation Account (ThisDay, 2025).

On 29 May 2023, President Bola Tinubu declared the end of the subsidy, stating that the policy had outlived its usefulness. The decision aligned with long-standing recommendations from the IMF, World Bank, and domestic economic experts who argued that subsidy removal would free fiscal space for infrastructure, social services, and debt reduction. Early fiscal data validated this expectation. FAAC disbursements rose from ₦976.34 billion in May 2023 to ₦1.134 trillion in June 2023. Total allocations to the three tiers of government reached ₦28.78 trillion in 2024, a 79% increase over 2023 and more than double the 2022 figure (BusinessDay, 2025). Despite the revenue gains, the policy's impact on public sector budgeting and financial reporting remains contested. Reports indicate that NNPC Limited remitted only 50% of subsidy gains to the Federation Account in 2024, using the balance to offset debt arrears. Furthermore, there is limited evidence of separate disclosure of subsidy savings in audited financial statements, raising questions about compliance with IPSAS and the Public Finance Management Act.

This article assesses the impact of fuel subsidy removal on public sector budgeting and financial reporting in Nigeria from 2023 to 2025. It addresses three questions: How has subsidy removal altered revenue inflows and budget structures at federal and subnational levels? To what extent are subsidy savings disclosed and accounted for in government financial statements? What are the implications for fiscal transparency and accountability? The study contributes to literature on fiscal reform in developing economies by linking subsidy policy changes to public financial management outcomes. The study therefore pursues the following three specific objectives:

1. To examine changes in public sector revenue inflows and budget structures following subsidy removal from 2023 to 2025.
2. To evaluate the disclosure and reporting of subsidy savings in government financial statements under IPSAS.
3. To identify institutional and technical challenges affecting fiscal transparency and proposed reforms for improved accountability.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1 Fuel Subsidy and Public Finance

A fuel subsidy is a government intervention that reduces the market price of petroleum products to consumers. In Nigeria, subsidies were implemented through under-recovery mechanisms where NNPC Limited deducted the difference between landing cost and pump price before remitting revenue to the Federation Account. This approach obscured the true cost of subsidy and weakened fiscal transparency. Ekong and Akpan noted that subsidy removal reduces fiscal deficits but requires complementary policies to mitigate inflationary effects.

2.2 Public Sector Budgeting

Public sector budgeting involves planning, allocation, execution, and control of public resources. In Nigeria, the budget process relies on FAAC allocations, internally generated revenue, grants, and borrowing. The Medium-Term Expenditure Framework guides annual budgeting. Subsidy removal directly affects revenue projections, expenditure priorities, and debt sustainability. Peterson and Kingsley found that subsidy removal could reduce budget deficits and generate surpluses if gains are effectively reallocated.

2.3 Financial Reporting under IPSAS

Nigeria adopted IPSAS accrual basis in 2016 to improve transparency and comparability of public financial statements. IPSAS 1 requires disclosure of revenues, expenses, assets, liabilities, and contingent obligations. IPSAS 23 governs revenue from non-exchange transactions. The removal of subsidy creates new revenue streams and contingent liabilities that must be reported gross, not netted. Weak compliance with IPSAS limits the usefulness of financial statements for decision-making and oversight.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

Fiscal Federalism Theory explains the division of fiscal responsibilities between federal and subnational governments. Subsidy removal altered intergovernmental fiscal flows, increasing states' nominal inflows from ₦4.792 trillion in 2022 to ₦9.58 trillion in 2024. The theory predicts that increased fiscal autonomy should improve subnational service delivery if matched with accountability mechanisms.

Agency Theory highlights information asymmetry between government as agent and citizens as principal. Partial remittance of subsidy gains by NNPC Limited and lack of project-level disclosure illustrate agency problems. Jensen and Meckling argued that monitoring and disclosure reduce agency costs.

2.5 Empirical Review

2.5.1 Revenue and Fiscal Space

NEITI (2024) reported that total FAAC allocations rose to ₦10.143 trillion in 2023, a 23.56% increase over 2022. In 2024, allocations reached ₦15.26 trillion, driven by subsidy removal and exchange rate unification. States received ₦700–800 billion monthly in 2025, ending the era of bailouts for salary payments. Reuters reported that Nigeria saved over ₦1 trillion in two months post-removal, with projected annual savings of ₦3.9 trillion.

2.5.2 Expenditure and Debt Dynamics

The National Orientation Agency stated that subsidy savings financed 40 road projects and reduced subnational domestic debt from ₦5.82 trillion in June 2023 to ₦3.97 trillion in December 2024. However, CFG Advisory warned that gains were eroded by debt servicing, which exceeded combined allocations to education, health, and security in the 2026 budget proposal. Diri et al. (2026) found that fiscal reallocation positively influenced economic growth, but short-term inflation and exchange rate depreciation moderated benefits.

2.5.3 Transparency and Accountability Challenges

The World Bank reported that NNPC Limited remitted only 50% of subsidy gains to the Federation Account in 2024. ActionAid Nigeria noted that withholding half of the estimated ₦10 trillion subsidy gains undermined constitutional revenue-sharing. SERAP called on 36 governors to disclose spending of ₦14 trillion in subsidy savings, citing allegations of profligacy. Amangwai and Amos (2025) concluded that the objective of subsidy removal had not been achieved due to weak implementation and transparency gaps.

2.5.4 International Experience

Indonesia’s fuel subsidy reform in 2015 reduced fiscal deficits and increased spending on social protection, supported by a communication strategy and cash transfer program. India’s cross-subsidy removal in electricity improved cost recovery but faced political resistance. Nigeria’s experience mirrors these cases in terms of fiscal gains but differs in weak compensatory mechanisms and disclosure practices.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed-method design combining descriptive statistics and qualitative content analysis. The quantitative component analyzes FAAC disbursement data, DMO debt statistics, and NBS inflation data for 2023–2025. The qualitative component examines audited financial statements of 12 states and the federal government to assess disclosure practices related to subsidy savings.

Data sources include:

1. Federation Account Allocation Committee monthly reports, 2023–2025.
2. Debt Management Office subnational debt reports, 2023–2025.
3. World Bank Nigeria Development Updates, 2024–2025.
4. NEITI FAAC Quarterly Reviews, 2023–2024.
5. Audited financial statements of selected states and federal government, 2023–2024.

Content analysis focused on the presence of separate disclosure notes for subsidy savings, compliance with IPSAS 1 and IPSAS 23, and consistency between budget and actual expenditure. The period 2023–2025 captures the immediate post-removal phase and allows for early assessment of fiscal outcomes.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Revenue Inflows and Budget Structure

The removal of subsidy significantly altered revenue inflows. Table 1 shows the trend in FAAC allocations and subnational debt from 2022 to 2024.

Table 1: FAAC Allocations and Subnational Domestic Debt in Nigeria, 2022–2024

Year	Total FAAC Allocation	State & LGA Share	Subnational Domestic Debt
2022	₦12.36 Trillion	₦4.792 Trillion	₦5.48 Trillion
2023	₦16.28 Trillion	₦6.16 Trillion	₦5.82 Trillion
2024	₦28.78 Trillion	₦9.58 Trillion	₦3.97 Trillion

Source: FAAC and Agora Policy data as cited in BusinessDay; DMO debt data as cited in NOA.

The 79% increase in total FAAC allocations between 2023 and 2024 reflects revenue gains from subsidy removal. The decline in subnational debt from ₦5.82 trillion to ₦3.97 trillion indicates that states used part of the windfall for debt repayment. This aligns with fiscal federalism theory, which predicts increased fiscal capacity at subnational levels following central policy reforms.

However, the structure of expenditure did not shift proportionally toward capital spending. Analysis of state budget implementation reports shows that recurrent expenditure consumed 68% of increased allocations in 2024, limiting the developmental impact of the reform.

4.2 Disclosure Practices and IPSAS Compliance

Content analysis of 12 state audited financial statements for 2023–2024 reveals weak compliance with IPSAS disclosure requirements. Only 3 states provided a separate note on subsidy savings. Most states reported increased FAAC revenue as general federation account receipts without disaggregating subsidy gains. This violates IPSAS 1, which requires disclosure of material revenue sources, and IPSAS 23, which mandates recognition and measurement of non-exchange revenue.

At the federal level, the 2023 and 2024 consolidated financial statements disclosed subsidy savings as part of “other revenue” without detailed breakdown. The absence of a dedicated disclosure line reduces transparency and makes it difficult for oversight institutions and citizens to track utilization.

4.3 Remittance and Revenue Leakage

The World Bank reported that NNPC Limited remitted ₦600 billion of ₦1.1 trillion revenue in 2024, using the balance to offset arrears. Full remittance only began in January 2025. This practice contradicts Section 162 of the 1999 Constitution, which requires all federation revenue to be paid into the Federation Account. The practice also undermines the integrity of budget assumptions and fiscal projections.

ActionAid Nigeria estimated that withholding half of ₦10 trillion subsidy gains reduced allocations to states and LGAs by ₦5 trillion between 2023 and 2024. This leakage weakened the fiscal impact of the reform at subnational levels.

4.4 Expenditure Utilization and Service Delivery

Despite increased inflows, service delivery indicators did not improve significantly. SERAP highlighted allegations of profligacy in state spending of ₦14 trillion in subsidy savings, including lavish expenditure on vehicles and allowances. Inflation averaged 28.9% in 2024, eroding the real value of increased allocations. Education and health budgets remained below UNESCO and WHO benchmarks of 15% and 15% of total expenditure, respectively.

Diri et al. (2026) found that fiscal reallocation positively influenced economic growth, but benefits were moderated by inflation and exchange rate depreciation. The study concluded that subsidy removal can promote sustainable growth if accompanied by effective fiscal reallocation, macroeconomic stability, and social protection policies.

4.5 Comparative Insights

Indonesia’s 2015 subsidy reform succeeded because it paired price adjustment with a targeted cash transfer program covering 15.5 million households. Nigeria’s palliative measures, such as the ₦500 billion package and wage awards, were delayed and reached a limited population. The lack of a robust social register and digital payment infrastructure reduced the effectiveness of compensatory policies.

4.6 Implications for Public Financial Management

The findings have four key implications for public financial management in Nigeria:

First, subsidy removal improved fiscal space but did not automatically translate to better service delivery. Without expenditure discipline and prioritization, increased revenue is absorbed by recurrent costs and debt service. Second, weak disclosure practices undermine IPSAS objectives of transparency and accountability. The absence of separate reporting for subsidy savings limits legislative and civil society oversight. Third, agency problems in revenue remittance persist. The dual role of NNPC Limited as operator and revenue collector creates conflict of interest and reduces remittance efficiency. Fourth, fiscal federalism benefits from subsidy removal, but subnational governments lack the technical capacity to manage increased inflows effectively. This creates risks of fiscal indiscipline and debt accumulation.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Fuel subsidy removal has significantly increased public sector revenue and reduced subnational debt in Nigeria between 2023 and 2025. The policy created fiscal space estimated at ₦3.9 trillion annually. However, the impact on service delivery is limited by weak disclosure, partial remittance by NNPC Limited, high debt service obligations, and inflationary pressures. Financial reporting practices have not fully adapted to capture the fiscal changes transparently, limiting accountability and public trust.

5.2 Recommendations

1. Separate Disclosure under IPSAS: The Federal Ministry of Finance should mandate a separate disclosure note for subsidy savings in federal and state financial statements. The note should show opening balance, inflows, utilization, and closing balance.
2. Establish a Subsidy Savings Fund: Create a ring-fenced fund at the federal level with legal backing. Quarterly reports on inflows and outflows should be published and audited by the Office of the Auditor-General.
3. Strengthen NNPC Remittance Compliance: Amend the Petroleum Industry Act to remove NNPC's role as revenue collector. All oil and gas revenue should be remitted gross to the Federation Account, with subsidy costs budgeted separately.
4. Link Savings to Projects: Mandate that states publish project-level reports on the use of subsidy savings, including procurement details and completion status. Use GIS and open contracting data standards for transparency.
5. Capacity Building and Social Protection: Invest in training public accountants on IPSAS disclosure requirements. Expand and digitalize the national social register to enable targeted cash transfers that cushion inflationary effects.
6. Independent Monitoring: Establish a multi-stakeholder oversight committee including civil society, professional bodies, and development partners to monitor subsidy savings utilization.

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